

Calibrating Trust and Enhancing User Agency in LLM-Based Chatbots through Conversational Styles

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This paper proposes a linguistic approach to trust in text-based conversational agents, such as LLM-based chatbots like ChatGPT. We argue that linguistic indicators of trust in human interaction should be tested to see if and how they can be applied to engage users in a trust-calibrated and user-agency enhancing interaction with LLM-based chatbots. Specifically, we consider conversational style, transparency about the status of LLM-based chatbots as next-word predictors, and human agency to be crucial aspects in the chatbot language design that promotes the calibration of trust in the capabilities, benevolence, and integrity of LLM-based chatbots. Furthermore, the proposed approach motivates users to think about the content, but also about how trust is expressed linguistically, and encourages them to think critically about the linguistic properties of chatbot responses.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: large language models, chatbots, trust calibration, linguistic indicators of trust, user agency, conversational style, transparency

ACM Reference Format:

Milena Belosevic and Hendrik Buschmeier. 2024. Calibrating Trust and Enhancing User Agency in LLM-Based Chatbots through Conversational Styles. In *CUI@CHI 2024 Workshop, May 11, 2024, Honolulu, Hawai'i*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 7 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10896068>

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper addresses trust in human-AI interactions by focusing on text-based conversational agents, such as LLM-based chatbots (ChatGPT, Gemini, etc.), as a subset of conversational user interfaces. In particular, it considers design techniques that foster trust calibration and user agency and argues that an appropriately calibrated conversational style, verbalized through linguistic trust cues, can affect the perceived trustworthiness of LLM-based chatbots. We propose to design chatbots that enhance the active role of users in trust calibration. Specifically, by offering users the opportunity to customize the response presented to them, they are implicitly encouraged to critically reflect on how the chatbot's conversational style influences the linguistic expression of an appropriate (calibrated) level of trust in the chatbot's responses.

Based on Mayer et al. [23, p. 717–719], we define trust as a multifaceted attitude that consists of the following three aspects: ability (“the group of skills that enable a [person] to have influence within some specific domain”), benevolence (“the extent to which a trustee is believed to want to do good to the trustor”), and integrity (“the trustor's perception that the trustee adheres to a set of principles that the trustor finds acceptable”). Furthermore, we distinguish between *trust*, as “the attitude that an agent will help achieve an individual's goal in a situation characterized by uncertainty and vulnerability” [18, p. 51], and *trustworthiness*, defined in terms of how trustors assign ability, benevolence, and integrity to trust objects. Trust is *calibrated* when users can adjust the level

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CUI@CHI 2024 Workshop, May 11, 2024, Honolulu, Hawai'i

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10896068>

of their perceived trust with the actual reliability of the agents ([25]; see Wischnewski et al. [36] for a recent overview).

Our starting point is the assumption that trust is constantly (re)negotiated in interaction [9] and that it can “only [be] reached by communication and communicative means in a linguistic process” [24, p. 85]. Similarly, Jucks et al. [14, p. 234] claim that “the choice of words is a vehicle for establishing trust in interpersonal online communication – regardless of whether it is written or spoken and whether the interaction is with another human or an artificial interlocutor”. However, trust measures based on linguistic cues still do not play a prominent role compared to well-established behavioral methods or questionnaires [6, 13]. In this paper, we propose to apply the linguistic cues that indicate trust in human-human interaction (*trust cues* [38]) to the study of trust in LLM-based chatbots. In this regard, Kuhnenn [17] identified the following four groups of linguistic cues used by trustees to express their trustworthiness:

- (1) competence (referring to own expertise or experts, use of technical terms),
- (2) social embedding (social competence of trustees: listener feedback, lexical alignment, empathy, irony, and humor),
- (3) reliability (referring to own previous coherent and consistent actions, admitting errors, providing consistent/non-contradictory statements, expressing the confidence level of own statements, providing promises regarding future actions),
- (4) comprehensibility (recipient-oriented word choice, use of an appropriate register, use of varied language, formal length and complexity of utterances, prosody, repetitions, use of examples).

Importantly, the cues are correlated and a combination of cues interactively forms a conversational style [30], which can generally be defined as the way something is said because “anything you say must be said at a certain rate, in certain words, at a certain pitch and amplitude, in certain intonation, at a certain point in the interaction” [33, p. 251]. In human interaction, interlocutors use linguistic resources to manage the interaction and actively choose to deploy them as means or cues that they tacitly know to fulfill a particular function or to suggest a particular interactional meaning [29]. Prosodic markers, for example, can display trust or distrust in human–human dialogue [10, 20]. As for trust, we assume that speakers, apart from signaling speech activity, also indicate their level of trust using verbal and nonverbal cues. The competence of trustees, the alignment of their actions with the actions of trustors, and putting oneself in the position of trustors (by displaying empathy and understanding) are crucial properties of trustworthy interlocutors [28]. These properties are verbalized by a consistent and coherent combination of linguistic trust cues. Which aspects are verbalized is context-dependent. We consider these aspects to be crucial for trust in LLMs. For example, the consistency of LLMs is related to the ability to generalize in the face of language variability [8], and the technique of alignment refers to the process of ensuring that LLMs verbalize human values and norms [21, 38].

2 TRUST IN INTERACTION WITH LLM-BASED CHATBOTS

Similar to trust in human interaction, research on trust in conversational user interfaces has mainly focused on behavioral methods and questionnaires [34], largely neglecting that trust is often established through linguistic means [3]. More recent studies, however, reflect on the role of communication-based aspects in measuring trust in automation [2, 16]. Trust has also been approached using different aspects closely related to trust, such as communication in uncertain and high-risk situations, apologies [15], or disclosure [32]. For instance, research has shown that people tend to disclose symptoms of depression more truthfully when talking to a chatbot than when talking to a human interviewer [19].

Finally, studies on human–chatbot trust emphasize that chatbot language design should not only consider what information is conveyed, but also how, e.g., in terms of conversational register. Chaves and Gerosa [5], for example, state that “user experience goes beyond merely comprehending a chatbot’s utterance to whether

the user perceives the chatbot’s language as appropriate and credible”. In this regard, recent studies show that a pleasant communication style along with the perception of ChatGPT as human-like or intelligent, a simple language, and a good structure and flow has a positive impact on user experience [31]. Similarly, Chaves et al. [4, p. 2] state that “when chatbots misuse language (e.g., conveying excessive (in)formality or using an incoherent style), the conversation sounds strange to the user, and leads to frustration”.

Regarding linguistic trust cues, to the best of our knowledge, no studies on human-automation trust have investigated whether and to what extent linguistic aspects account for trust in non-human interlocutors and whether linguistic trust markers from human interaction can be transferred to human-chatbot interaction. Recent studies focus on linguistic indicators of deception and honesty in human vs. AI language [11, 22], or investigate similarities with human trust behavior in trust games [37]. We postulate that if LLM-based chatbots mimic human language capabilities, they should display similar linguistic trust cues as human interlocutors and mimic the characteristics of trustworthy interlocutors mentioned above (competence, aligning one’s actions with the actions of trustors, and putting oneself in the position of trustors). The latter two aspects would, however, increase the anthropomorphic character of chatbots. This raises ethical concerns and could again lead to trust miscalibration [1]. We thus propose a design that increases the role of the user in trust calibration and relies on user agency.

3 IMPLICATIONS FOR USER DESIGN

In the following, we propose how LLM-based chatbots could be designed with the help of linguistic trust markers in order to improve trust calibration by enhancing user agency.

Consider the example from the healthcare domain that is illustrated in Figure 1-A. After submitting a prompt to ChatGPT (v3.5), we received a response beginning with “I am not a doctor, but ...”. From the perspective of linguistic research on trust, this response is incoherent. ChatGPT ‘admits’ that it is not a doctor, but still provides medical recommendations. This is a typical example of a poorly calibrated chatbot response that violates the aspects of trust described above: ChatGPT provides contradictory information about its competence, and by trying to align its actions (providing help) with the actions of a human trustor (seeking advice), it does not align with human values (honesty). The aspect “putting oneself in the position of trustors” is not verbalized in this case. Note, however, that ChatGPT later recommends seeking medical help – but its response begins with the miscalibrated sentence.

We propose an interaction design for linguistic trust calibration where miscalibrated parts of the response (e.g., “I am not a doctor”) are highlighted. When the user clicks on a highlight, a dialog box (blue speech bubble) appears with options for calibrating the miscalibrated part of the response (see Figure 1-B). Users can select the option they find most appropriate in a given context. The linguistic trust markers included in this dialog box should be context-sensitive and adaptable to different user groups. Although some LLM-based chatbots now offer customization options, these are not related to trust-relevant aspects (competence, alignment, etc.), but limited to the length or language style of responses (e.g., casual vs. formal). Engaging with the content of the dialogue box should motivate the user to critically reflect on the trustworthiness of a response and to practice AI literacy. After selecting one option, the user receives feedback from the chatbot about the selected conversational style, enhancing the chatbot’s transparency and self-disclosure. Importantly, users are also free to select a conversational style without linguistic trust cues. In this case, they should be warned by the appropriate description of the conversational style.

Since the proposed design relies on human evaluation of conversational styles, trust calibration is a process in which human users play an active role, it is co-constructed [27] by chatbots and users. Central empirical questions that arise are how (explicitly or implicitly, i.e., using lexical units, such as *trust*, *trustworthiness*, *reliable*, *distrust*, etc., or more implicit linguistic units) trust should be calibrated in the blue dialogue box, how to adjust the use of trust-related vocabulary to different user groups, and how to computationally model linguistic expressions

Fig. 1. Illustration of the proposed linguistic trust calibration for LLM chatbots. (A) The miscalibrated chatbot response. (B) The miscalibrated part is highlighted and the user can (optionally) click on it. A dialog box (blue bubble) then allows them to critically reflect and select a conversational style. They receive feedback in which the chatbot explicitly discloses its non-human nature.

of trustworthiness and perceived trust of users. To this end, this paper brings together concepts from several disciplines: research on trust in human interaction, trust calibration usually studied in the context of trust in automation, the impact of conversational style on trust in automation, and user agency from the research on user design.

The main practical implication of the design proposal can be observed by looking at the human-like verbal behavior of LLM-based chatbots (anthropomorphism), particularly in the context of benevolence as a property of trust. For instance, for ethical reasons, chatbots should not suggest medication and/or provide medical advice after previously warning about their ontological status. If that happens, the inconsistent conversational style should be appropriately presented to the user (e.g., by pointing to the discrepancy between the initial statement and the recommendation). Several studies confirm the positive impact of chatbot customization on users' perceived trust

but do not deal with the role of language [26, 35]. If users were able to compare different conversational styles and customize responses, they would realize that LLM chatbots cannot interact in the same manner as human interlocutors.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

In this position paper, we emphasized the role of users' AI literacy in evaluating the trustworthiness of chatbot responses and the importance of defining trust as a linguistic expression of a trust-calibrated communication style. Although the idea of promoting user agency and improving human control during interactions with conversational agents is not new [see 7], the use of linguistic cues to calibrate trust has not been explored as a method of trust calibration in work on trust in automation. Recommendations published by developers – such as those related to the usage of Google's Generative AI technology (“Think critically about the responses you get from generative AI tools. Use Google and other resources to check information that's presented as fact” [12]) – should be integrated into the conversation with users through linguistic trust markers and accompanied by the information about the non-human nature of a chatbot. In this way, transparency and openness regarding the chatbot's conversational capabilities could be enhanced.

Experimental studies should test which type of linguistic trust cues should be placed at which part of the answer (beginning, end), as well as whether and which trust indicators from human interaction are perceived as linguistic trust indicators when interacting with LLM-based chatbots. From the perspective of a conversation design practitioner, it is also crucial to investigate which factors influence the user's selection of a particular conversational style and how users react to the selected style during the conversation. From this perspective, the user's choice can be framed as their critical stance towards LLM-based chatbots, the level of their knowledge about LLM-typical conversational style, and the degree of their awareness about the concept of “pretending to be a human interlocutor”. Overall, we consider linguistic trust calibration in the form of the design proposed here to be an important technique for mitigating overreliance and practicing AI literacy.

Given that conversational styles comprise both verbal and nonverbal aspects, future studies should explore how the proposed method applies to voice-based conversational assistants, embodied virtual agents, and social robots. Studying users' non-verbal behavior during their interaction with voice-based agents, such as gaze or gestures, could provide further insights into the perceived trustworthiness of LLM-based chatbots and the correlation between verbal and nonverbal cues. Apart from benefits, disadvantages regarding the duration of conversations that do not immediately provide an answer but motivate users to reflect on the information given by a chatbot as well as the willingness of different user groups to engage in the critical reflection of responses should be considered as important aspects in chatbot design.

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